

CERTIFICATE

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RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALIDA

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN PROTECTING THE RIGHTS OF

CONSUMERS IN THE FIELD OF ELECTRONIC COMMERCE

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